

SIMULATION OF THE SINGLE Z-PIN PULL-OUT TEST BY THE FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

Nam Ju Lee¹, Chung-Ki Sim¹ and Seong Kyun Cheong²

¹ Dept. of Mechanical Engineering, Graduate School, Seoul National University of Science and Technology, Seoul, Korea

² Dept. of Mechanical and Automotive Engineering, Seoul National University of Science and Technology, Seoul, Korea, skjung@seoultech.ac.kr

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ABSTRACT

To overcome disadvantage of the composite laminates, many enhancement method is proposed but it is very powerful that the z-pinning method which is to insert the pin into the composite laminates through the out-of-plane direction(z-direction). In this study, we simulate the single pin pull-out test by using the finite element method and estimate the maximum pull-out force. Consequently, the interface stiffness is 75 N/mm³ and the strength is 13 MPa and the separation is 0.16 mm. We can obtain these properties from the real single pin pull-out test using the finite element method and verify that the maximum pull-out force value is similar in the two manner. In the near future, we expect that we can study the parameters about the change of its various dimension and shape.

1 INTRODUCTION

Low interlaminar fracture characteristics of composite laminates are well known in view of delamination resistance and low impact damage. The weaving, stitching and braiding techniques to increase the interlaminar strength have been proposed in the previous works. However, those techniques are not enough for reinforcing the composite laminates. Z-pinning is an effective technique to reinforce the through-the-thickness direction of composite laminates[1]. When the z-pin inserted in the composite laminates is pulled out, the pin undergoes the elastic deformation, the debonding and friction between the pin and counterpart. In this process, the functional relationship between closer force and delamination crack-opening from a single pin is called the bridging law which is related to reinforcement efficiency of z-pin[2,6]. The previous sentence means that it is very difficult to understand physical characters of the z-pin and to predict what is going to happen. In this study, to understand the physical properties of the interface between the pin and matrix, a single pin pull-out (SPP) test is performed and the maximum pull-out force value through the finite element method (FEM) will be found.

Figure 1: The single pin pull-out test (a) description of specimen (b) installed specimen.

2 SINGLE PIN PULL-OUT TEST

The carbon fiber pins and pull-out test specimen are made using the UD CFRP-prepreg(SK-Chemicals, USN 125B)[7]. The test specimen was laminated with 80 layers of prepregs in the quasi-isotropic sequence as shown in Figure 1. Then, the pin was inserted into the test specimen and co-cured. Adhesive bonding was applied on the opposite side of the specimen. Experiments were conducted using Instron 5948 and crosshead speed is 1.27mm/min.

3 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

3.1 Characteristic of the single pin pull-out test

Figure 2 shows the single pin pull-out(SPP) test results. The results show the linear relationship between pull-out force and displacement, which is very similar to the double cantilever beam(DCB) test results of previous works[2,5]. SPP test is to get the mechanical properties of the interface between the pin and matrix which is in enhanced composite materials by the pin. For the DCB test, it is difficult to catch the influence of a single pin because of the relatively strong adhesive strength of laminates. Also, it needs more consumption expense rather than the SSP test. Anyway, SSP test results display the debonding initiation time(δ_i, P_i) and debonding end time(δ_f, P_f) in Fig. 2. In this study, the maximum pull-out force value at the debonding initiation time in SSP test will be fit by using FEM. Thus, pull-out force and displacement relation by the friction between the pin and composite materials end time is not considered after debonding.

3.2 Cohesive model

Figure 3 indicates that the interface between the pin and matrix has different mechanical behavior according to each orientations. Also, it is very important to understand physical properties of the interface between the pin and matrix because the interface governs the thickness-direction characters(e.g. stiffness, strength, etc.) of the enhanced composite materials by z-pins. K_i is the interface stiffness, T_i is the interface strength, δ_i is the interface separation($i=1,2,3$). These properties are shown in Figure 4. Damage modelling is typical method to express the cohesive behavior of the interface between the pin and matrix as shown in Fig. 4[4, 5].

$$\text{Max}(\langle t_i \rangle / T_1, t_2 / T_2, t_3 / T_3) = 1 \quad (1)$$

The symbol $\langle \rangle$ is the Macaulay bracket, t_i ($i=1, 2, 3$) is the dependent traction value[8]. Equation (1) means that if the maximum value by any component reaches 1, damage will be initiated. In order words, damage initiation means that the debonding starts. So, the equation (1) can be used for getting the debonding initiation time.

Figure 2: Assumption of the single pin pull-out test data.

4 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

It needs considerable efforts to carry out the test in the restricted conditions, for example, material cost, limited time and labor, etc. To solve these problems, many researchers largely have been using the FEM which is a part of numerical method[3-5]. In this paper, ABAQUS was chosen as a FEM solver. Figure 5 shows the dimensions and boundary conditions of the finite element model. The material properties are shown in Table 1. The convergence test was accomplished to increase the reliability and the number of nodes and elements in this problem are 150,000 and 140,000 respectively. Also, we allocate the biased mesh shape around the interface between the pin and matrix to make the contact which is non-linear analysis process to get the exact solutions.

Figure 3: Typical behavior of the z-pin and counterpart.

Figure 4: Schematic of traction-separation law

5 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As mentioned earlier, our focus is to get the close FEM results like the maximum pull-out force obtained through the real test. First, we should assume that the interface between the pin and matrix is isotropic and was governed by the shear behavior for simplifying the FEM process. That is to say, K_2 , T_2 , δ_2 determine the pull-out force. Actually, various $K_{1,3}$, $T_{1,3}$, $\delta_{1,3}$ does not affect the FEM results. Next, choose the arbitrary K_2 and find the specified K_2 which indicate the FEM results similar to the real SSP test results. Lastly, determine the T_2 , δ_2 like the previous process.

Figure 6 visually shows the procedure looking for the specified K_2 , T_2 . Figure 7 simultaneously demonstrates the FEM results using the determined K_2 , T_2 and the SSP test results simultaneously. It seems that the maximum pull-out force of the SSP test results consist with the maximum value of the FEM results well. Also, the FEM results imply that the SSP test can be simulated under diverse situations using determined interface properties(K_2 , T_2 , δ_2). For instance, the parametric study can be implemented about various dimensions or diverse shapes of the z-pin. Furthermore, the various test methods like the DCB test, end-notched-flexure(ENF) test or single-lap test, etc. may be simulated.

Figure 5: Dimensions and B. C. of the FEM model.

Engineering Constant	Dimension	Value
E_1	[GPa]	128
$E_2 = E_3$	[GPa]	8.5
$G_{12} = G_{13}$	[GPa]	4.5
G_{23}	[GPa]	3.5
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	-	0.32
ν_{23}	-	0.47

Table 1: The CFRP material properties(SK-Chemicals, USN 125B)

Figure 6: FEM results by variable interface cohesive (a) K_2 [N/mm^3], (b) T_2 [MPa].

Figure 7: Comparing FEM results and experiment data(δ_2 is [mm]).

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